

Nonlinearity mitigation in systems with distributed Raman amplification

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Abstract: Distributed Raman amplification has become an essential element in the optical communication system designer toolbox, offering extended bandwidth and improved noise performance. But gain distribution can offer additional advantages when coupled with nonlinearity mitigation techniques, whether digital or based on physical effects. In this talk we will explore the advantages and limitations of distributed Raman amplification in the context of high-capacity optical communication systems with nonlinear mitigation.

In recent years, several techniques have been proposed to compensate or partially mitigate impairments due to fiber nonlinear effects, as growing demand pushes optical communication channel capacity close to its theoretical limit for standard single-mode fibre [1-3]. At the same time, distributed Raman amplification [4] has become a key tool in long-haul and unrepeated optical transmission system design, as it allows for the extension of the usable spectral bandwidth and offers improved noise performance when compared to more traditional lumped optical amplification solutions.

In this presentation we will explore the potential marriage of different nonlinearity mitigation techniques [5-9] with distributed Raman amplification showing that, indeed, the latter can in some cases be used to enhance the performance of the former.

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